

A series of decorative blue bars in various shades and widths, including a long dark blue bar at the top, a medium blue bar with a white horizontal line, and several vertical bars of varying heights and widths in different shades of blue.

Comprehensive Resource Collection: University Libraries in Crisis Response: Data, Engagement and Advocacy

Author: Korina Defteraiou, Katerina Zourou (Web2Learn)

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Partnership

	Name	Logo
1	University of Tartu	
2	Web2Learn	
3	Kaunas University of Technology	
4	Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies	
5	SKS Knowledge Services	

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1. Executive Summary

This comprehensive collection of resources maps out existing practices and initiatives related to libraries' roles in crises, highlighting current practices and theoretical frameworks. Specifically, it provides a comprehensive view of library responses in multiple crises related to socio-environmental and geopolitical challenges that we face today.

The objective of this collection is to serve as a foundational element for understanding the current landscape of libraries' role in crises management. The resources are categorised based on the 5 themes related to CAELUM case studies: 1. mental health/well-being, 2. employability, 3. disability, 4. dis/misinformation in conflict, 5. open data/science.

Overall, the collection contributes to better understanding of the state of the art in library crises response and aspires to identify effective strategies and uncover gaps in existing approaches to crisis response across university libraries.

All the resources figure in the open access repository of the project:

<https://caelum.ut.ee/collection-of-resources/>

About CAELUM

CAELUM (Open science supporting vulnerable communities: empowering university libraries in crisis response, 2025-2027, <https://caelum.ut.ee/>) is a 2-year Erasmus+ project that places university libraries in the forefront of crisis response through open science, supporting vulnerable communities and bolstering EU-UA cooperation. Through a series of activities, CAELUM aims to upskill university libraries' staff in innovative and interdisciplinary approaches to crisis response and promote and sustain university libraries-driven open knowledge and civic engagement among HE students and staff for crisis response. Thus, CAELUM empowers university libraries in leveraging open and citizen science approaches as well as community engagement practices for crisis response in multiple contexts.

2.Scope and Methodology

The collection of resources aims to map out existing practices and initiatives related to university libraries' roles in crises, by collecting a diverse range of resources, thus serving as a foundational element for understanding the current landscape of libraries' role in crisis.

Methodology

The development of the WP2A1 collection of resources was based on a 4-stage methodological framework. In particular:

Stage 1: Inventory creation. The authors created an inventory (excel file) that was validated by the University of Tartu (project's coordinator). Then, it was shared with all project partners along with instructions. The inventory included the following descriptors:

- Partner
- Name of the resource
- Country (where the initiative was identified)
- Type of crisis
- Is it connected to one of the 5 Caelum themes? (y/n)
- If yes, choose which one (drop down items)
- Role of academia /library?
- Type of action
- Is a library engaged in this
- Link to the resource

All CAELUM partners were asked to fill in the inventory with resources and data, in any language, regarding existing practices and initiatives related to university libraries' roles in crises.

Stage 2: Data screening and validation. Following partners' contributions to stage 1, the authors carefully screened all the data regarding their relevance with the WP2A1's scope.

Stage 3: Synthesize sample in the repository. All the selected actions were categorised based on the 5 themes related to CAELUM case studies:

1. mental health/well-being,
2. employability,
3. disability,
4. dis/misinformation in conflict,
5. open data/science.

and then synthesized based on the following features:

- Title
- Full reference (only for scientific papers)
- URL
- Summary
- Role of library
- Type of action

Stage 4: Peer review by Kaunas University of Technology. After the synthesis of the repository, KTU as QA leader of the project reviewed it and provided feedback that was integrated to the final version of the repository that included 45 resources were shortlisted.

3. Annex

Mental health/well-being

Playing for keeps: How academic libraries are prioritizing student mental health and well-being through play

Nance, M. K., (2022), Playing for Keeps: How academic libraries are prioritizing student mental health and well-being through play, The Journal of Play in Adulthood 4(2), 162-176. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5920/jpa.1026>

Summary: A paper about the role of academic libraries in supporting the mental health and wellbeing of their communities by developing methods of play. Most commonly art supplies, videogame consoles/games, and kinetic resources such as Legos and Play-Doh are offered year-round for check out at many institutions, while events including coloring and crafting opportunities are offered monthly with an increased presence near midterms and finals. This paper has utilized a combination of annual reports, scholarly articles, and library websites to identify and convey trends, emerging practices, and initiatives.

Role of library: Academic libraries offer art supplies, videogame consoles/games, and kinetic resources for supporting students' mental health and host play-based activities and events to support students' mental health.

Type of action: Proactive intervention, supporting students by providing resources, such as games, and organising activities and events.

How the University library is becoming the hub of mental health support

<https://www.cilip.org.uk/news/596257/How-the-University-library-is-becoming-the-hub-of-mental-health-support.htm>

Summary: An article about the role of the academic library of Middlesex University to support the mental health and well-being of their students. The article analyses how the library responded to mental health issues among students, after the increased mental health issues during and after the pandemic.

Role of library: The university library plays a key role in supporting student mental health by serving as a safe and accessible space, offering wellbeing resources, organizing student support initiatives, and collaborating with university and external mental health services. It also works with safeguarding officers and peer support networks to assist students.

Type of action: Support and referral, resource provision, community building, collaboration with external mental health services.

Empowering minds: libraries leading the charge in student mental health (Video on YouTube channel)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0ukkEidI-Vg>

Summary: In the wake of the global mental health crisis, exacerbated by the Covid-19 pandemic, the demand for mental health services has reached unprecedented levels, leaving universities grappling with the challenge of providing adequate support. Libraries have emerged as crucial allies in this endeavor, acting as knowledge hubs and offering vital resources to address the pressing mental health needs of students and researchers.

Role of library: The library plays a role in supporting student mental health by organizing wellness programs, offering designated safe spaces, normalizing mental health discussions, and providing bibliotherapy resources. Libraries serve as a central hub where students can access mental health information, take breaks from academic stress, and engage in supportive activities.

Type of action: Support and referral, community engagement, educational programming, resource curation

How can academic libraries help support students' mental health?

Hunter C. (2021), How can academic libraries help support students' mental health? Reflective Professional, 1.

<https://doi.org/10.48525/rp-2021-id130>

Summary: The aim of the research was to investigate how academic libraries can positively impact on student mental health and wellbeing. This was done through a phenomenological mixed methods research which included student focus groups and a survey of UK academic library staff. The results of the student focus groups, and staff survey showed that both students and staff felt positively towards the idea of mental health and wellbeing support in libraries, however, both students and staff did express concerns about what the support would entail and how it would be enacted.

Role of library: Libraries become a safe space for students by offering de-stress activities, resources relevant to bibliotherapy and relaxation spaces. Moreover, libraries can signpost to mental health support services and train the staff for basic mental health first aid.

Type of action: Preventive measures, educational initiatives, provision of resources, upskilling the librarians for mental health issues.

The Library as a Safe Place: Methodological Tips for Librarians on Creating Safe Spaces in Libraries [available in Ukrainian]

Luhova L., Sachynska O., (2022) The Library as a Safe Place: Methodological Tips for Librarians on Creating Safe Spaces in Libraries, Goethe-Institut Ukraine, NGO Ukrainian Library Association - Kyiv: ULA, 42 p.

<https://ula.org.ua/images/documents/5062/Safe%20place%20Library.pdf>

Summary: A practical guide to transform public library spaces into shelter spaces in military conflicts. Libraries could become a safe environment for local populations in emergency situations. This guide offers methodological advice for librarians to transform libraries in safe places for citizens in conflicts and environmental hazard zones.

Role of library: Libraries can have a role in conflicts as shelters in emergency situations. Thus, libraries could be transformed to safe spaces for the physical well-being of the local populations.

Type of action: Methodological advice and guideline for the librarians in military crisis

Developing a Sense of Community in the Activities of the University Library of Ukraine in Wartime (on the Example of the Scientific Library of USUST)

Kolesnykova, T. O., & Demidko, M. M. (2024), Developing a Sense of Community in the Activities of the University Library of Ukraine in Wartime (on the Example of the Scientific Library of USUST), University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development, Conference Proceedings, (9), 191–203. https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2024_319086

Summary: In Ukraine, the deepening of the global crisis as a result of the COVID 2019 pandemic is exacerbated by Russia's war of aggression. University libraries of Ukraine in the socio-cultural situation of wartime have proved their ability to provide information support for learning and research. The publication analyses the case of the Scientific Library of USUST in Dnipro as an example of the transformation of the social, informational and communication role of the library in emergency situations.

Role of library: The Library organised joint activities with citizens to restoring mental health. It also organised leisure practices aimed at fostering the values of the democratic world, with conscious and active involvement of citizens in public life, openness of knowledge, barrier-free access, tolerance, and patriotism.

Type of action: Activities, open knowledge and free access.

Scientific and Technical Library of Vinnytsia National Technical University

<https://ir.lib.vntu.edu.ua/bitstream/handle/123456789/35892/Prytulyak%20%20T..pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

Summary: A non-academic publication about the role of the Scientific and Technical Library of Vinnytsia National Technical University of Ukraine in community support, resource provision, digital access and information diffusion.

Role of library: The University's Library has a significant role in maintaining access to information and in providing social support to students.

Type of action: Volunteering activities, community support, access to knowledge and information

Library of the Ukrainian Catholic University [available in Ukrainian]

<https://center.ucu.edu.ua/biblioteka-novyny/blagodijnyj-projekt-biblioteky-uku-hochu-chytaty/>

Summary: A project of the Library of the Ukrainian Catholic University that aims to collect books and funds for the restoration of libraries in destroyed schools. Thus, the project aims to support the Ukrainian language, education, and culture through books and reading. The library makes an appeal for books donation and is also in contact with volunteers in different European cities for sending books to refugees from Ukraine in Europe who need books in their native language.

Role of library: The Library offers support to Ukrainian refugees through provision of books and collects book for the restoration of libraries in destroyed schools due to military actions/

Type of action: Volunteering activities, community support, social support, European cooperation

The university library in the military realities of a front-line city [available in Ukrainian]

Kyrychok, I. V. (2023), University Library in the Military Realities of a Frontline City. V Scientific and Practical Conference with International Participation "Libraries and Society: Movement in Time and Space", Kharkiv, KhNMU Scientific Library. URL:

<https://repo.knmu.edu.ua/server/api/core/bitstreams/7b628952-9602-4e6a-9987-91dd28d70d8c/content>

Summary: A scientific paper about the challenges faced by Ukrainian higher education and university libraries, during the Russian military aggression. The university libraries are presented as research facilitators that also support mental health during the war.

Role of library: The Library facilitates research, provides medical information and promotes mental health.

Type of action: Research initiatives, information dissemination

The Role of Libraries in Meeting the Challenges of Democratic Society [available in Lithuanian]

<https://www.lnb.lt/vaizdo-irasai/tiesiogines-transliacijos/11795-lietuvos-ir-ukrainos-forumas-biblioteku-vaidmuo-sprendziant-demokratines-visuomenes-issukius>

Summary: A video by Martinas Mažvydas National Library of Lithuania on the Lithuanian-Ukrainian Forum. The 4-day Forum has been broadcasted live with 15 representatives of Ukrainian libraries and over 200 representatives from Lithuania. The aim of the Forum is to develop cooperation between Lithuanian and Ukrainian libraries in order to share knowledge and best practices, empowering libraries to contribute to overcoming the current challenges. The topics of the forum was the following: strengthening a democratic society, through networking, integration, development of emotional resilience and development of media and information literacy in libraries. Moreover, discussions were held about the local community initiatives, services and practices aimed at
Role of library: Libraries as hubs for promoting the values of a democratic society.
Type of action: Presentations, debates, practical presentations of library products, services and tools.

Informational Needs of Ukrainian Citizens in Klaipeda, by the Ieva Simonaitytė Klaipeda Public Library

<https://tvrc.lt/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Sociological-study-by-Tetiana-Virovka.pdf>

Summary: As a result of the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022 more than 73,000 Ukrainian refugees were displaced to Lithuania. Information provision for displaced persons is of great importance for adaptation in society. As part of the implementation of the project of the Lithuanian Cultural Council, Ieva Simonaitytė Klaipeda Public Library, conducted a sociological research, "Information Needs of Ukrainian Citizens in Klaipėda". The research aims to determine the information needs of displaced persons and the extent to which they are met by relevant services, and institutions, including libraries.

Role of library: The libraries as providers of information services to displaced Ukrainian refugees in Lithuania

Type of action: Library services provided to different categories of displaced persons for helping them to integrate in the host country.

Guidelines for Libraries Supporting Displaced Persons, by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

<https://repository.ifla.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/c9170b09-6b01-426e-a7b3-f59fff246792/content>

Summary: Libraries are transforming themselves into being the living room of society. In this time of the largest global refugee crisis since the second world war, libraries play a key role in making these new community members feel welcome and succeed in their efforts to develop themselves, heal their traumas and move on. Libraries play a pivotal role in empowering displaced individuals, safeguarding human rights, and fostering cultural understanding. Their responsibility as allies in safeguarding cultural memory and heritage benefits both host and origin societies, promoting positive social interaction.

Role of library: Apart from being a safe haven for all, libraries also contribute to the two-way integration process; not only do they help displaced individuals recover from their traumas and integrate into the host communities, but they also allow both displaced and host communities to learn from each other and understand their differences.

Type of action: Guidelines for training staff, building partnerships, assessing needs of displaced persons and evaluating services provided.

Employability

Libraries Ireland: Employment Support website

https://www.librariesireland.ie/employment-support?utm_source

Summary: Libraries Ireland has created a website page with a collection of resources by the public libraries in Ireland relating to job seeking and employment accessible to library members. The website offers online courses as well as eBooks and eAudiobooks for acquiring new skills and language learning courses. Moreover it includes guidelines how to build a CV and daily newspapers to help the search for employment opportunities. According to the website, library staff is available to help with any related query.

Role of library: Libraries as an information hub to job seekers and librarians are available help with any related queries.

Type of action: Provision of online resources related to job seeking and employment as well as help by the library staff.

Bibliothèque publique d'information Centre Pompidou: You are a job seeker

<https://www.bpi.fr/en/practical-information/offers-by-type-of-visitor/job-seeker/>

Summary: A website for informing the job-hunters about the services provided by the Bibliothèque publique d'information Centre Pompidou. It informs about the Careers Advice and Training space that offers information about academic and careers advice, the Self training space that is dedicated to lifelong independent learning, the Employment and Career workshops led by professional partners from the Cité des métiers (profession orientation structure) and the Independent Learning space that provides workshops to practice English, Spanish, Portuguese or French.

Role of library: The library operates as a training place with workshops, courses offered to the job seekers who also want to acquire new skills and as a counselling centre for advices and information about employment opportunities.

Type of action: Training courses, language workshops, independent learning, counselling services.

New York Public Library: Looking for Work?

<https://www.nypl.org/adults/career-services/for-job-seekers>

Summary: The Library helps to the search for employment with everything from resume help to databases to classes. It offers career coaching, workshops, online resources such as: eBooks, Audiobooks, and Videos for job seekers and entrepreneurs, downloadable by library members. It also offers recommendations for the best free websites for finding a job and advancing the career as well as other online search tools for employment opportunities.

Role of library: The library is a hub for information about employment opportunities as well as a center of learning of new skills and career coaching.

Type of action: Online resources, databases and search tools, workshops, career coaching.

Florida International University Libraries: Career & Talent Development Resources

<https://library.fiu.edu/career/International>

Summary: A collection of useful resources for international students that search job: job search websites, visa and immigration information, career information, list of business and industry research information as well as a list of books in the library that are helpful for jobseekers.

Role of library: The library has the role of information and advice provider.

Type of action: Collection of resources, books and databases for international students that search for job.

Drexel University Library

<https://libguides.library.drexel.edu/c.php?g=176932&p=1163396>

Summary: The Library has created a website page with practical information and guidance for job seekers. More particular, it offers personality tests, career tests, instructions how to write cover letters and tools to create high quality resume. Moreover, the Library proposes helpful books for career pursuit.

Role of library: Advisory and supportive to prepare students for the job market.

Type of action: Provision of practical information and guidance.

Disability

Changing lives: inclusive library practices for people with visual impairments and military rehabilitation in Rivne

<https://blog.lib4you.org.ua/zminyuyuchy-zhyttya-inklyuzyvna-praktyka-biblioteky-dlya-lyudej-z-porushennyamy-zoru-ta-reabilitacziya-vijskovyh-u-rivnomu/>

Summary: A program that aims at social rehabilitation of servicemen with visual impairments by implementing a comprehensive approach. The libraries transform into rehabilitation centers for military personel with vision problems in Rivne.

Role of library: The transformation of libraries into special inclusive rehabilitation centers for servicemen affected by the war in Ukraine.

Type of action: Provision of rehabilitation services to vulnerable groups affected by conflict and emergencies.

Lithuanian Culture Institute: Translations of Lithuanian literature into Ukrainian

<https://english.lithuanianculture.lt/news/2022/07/11/for-the-first-time-ever-books-by-lithuanian-authors-in-ukraine-will-be-available-in-audio-format/>

Summary: The Lithuanian Culture Institute, the Lithuanian Library for the Blind and the Lviv branch of the Assembly of Persons with Disabilities of Ukraine signed a cooperation agreement, which will provide an opportunity to release books by Lithuanian authors translated into Ukrainian in audio format and make them accessible to everyone, including those with special reading needs, those who like to listen to literature being read, and those learning Ukrainian.

Role of library: Access to knowledge, adjustment to special reading needs.

Type of action: Cooperation of the Library with other institutions for the translation of Lithuanian authors into Ukrainian in audio formats accessible to people with special reading needs.

Accessible library services

<https://www oulu.fi/en/university/library/library-services/accessible-services>

Summary: Oulu University Library has created an accessibility guide and customer service staff helps persons with disabilities regarding the use of the library's collections and facilities. Library's accessibility guide aims to provide information about the accessibility services in the different facilities of the libraries.

Role of library: A comprehensive guide for persons with disabilities that describes the facilities, services and equipment that are accessible to persons with disabilities.

Type of action: Provision of accessibility information to disabled persons.

Support for students and staff with disabilities: Library support and services

<https://library.bath.ac.uk/library-services-for-users-with-disabilities>

Summary: The University of Bath Library has created a guide for services the Library offers in support of students and staff with disabilities. The guide provides detailed information on the Assistive Technology rooms and the sensory room, both of which are situated in the Library.

Role of library: A guide for persons with disabilities that aims to provide equal opportunities for all users of the Library's services and facilities.

Type of action: Provision of support (Assistive Technology, Sensory room) and physical access to students and staff with disabilities.

Accessibility Resources & Services: Staff Training & Resources

<https://library.ccnycunyu.edu/c.php?g=535291&p=5691402>

Summary: The City College of New York provides a resource guide for library accessibility and assistive technology. A website dedicated to providing freely available self-paced training support for library staff, helping staff to be prepared to offer optimal support to students with disabilities.

Role of library: The library offers a guide with resources that are available for training of the library staff regarding accessibility and support to students with disabilities. The role of library is informative and educational.

Type of action: Provision of resources.

Library Services for Persons with Disabilities

<https://library.albany.edu/services/persons-with-disabilities>

Summary: The Library at the University at Albany provides a variety of services to persons with disabilities designed to enhance their ability to use the Library fully and independently. A webpage to guide persons with disabilities in accessing the services and a Disability Service Coordinator to help with any questions.

Role of library: Supportive and provision of accessible services.

Type of action: Provision of a guide.

Library Equipment & Facilities Management: Library Service to Persons with Disabilities

<https://libguides.ala.org/equip-facilities-mgt/disabilities>

Summary: The American Library Association (ALA) has created a resource guide that provides information on ALA policies and resources for library service to persons with disabilities, information on ALA working groups, a selected bibliography, and other online resources.

Role of library: Informative and supportive.

Type of action: Resource guide.

Inclusive libraries and supporting disabled users in science

<https://www.springernature.com/gp/librarians/the-link/dei-blogpost/libraries-inclusivity-digital-resources/27700986>

Summary: A blog article that describes best practices for making the digital resources accessible and underlines the importance of accessibility to library resources. The article gives advice on "How to make the library more accessible" and underscores the need of inclusive libraries.

Role of library: Provision of accessible library resources.

Type of action: Inclusive digital resources for disabled users.

Eugenides Foundation: Workstations in the library for disabled persons

<https://www.eef.edu.gr/en/visit/accessibility/in-the-library/>

Summary: The Eugenides Foundation has created and equipped workstations in the Library for ensuring that disabled people have equal access to all printed and electronic information. The stations can be used by: visually impaired people and people with mobility impairment (mainly in the upper limbs or quadriplegia).

Role of library: Provision of workstations for disabled users

Type of action: Provision of equipment and facilities that ensure the equal access of disabled persons to the library resources.

National Library of Greece (NLG) collaborates with the NPO "Me Alla Matia" [available in Greek]

<https://meallamatia.services/blog/2022/11/11/%CE%B7-%CE%B5%CE%B8%CE%BD%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AE-%CE%B2%CE%B9%CE%B2%CE%BB%CE%B9%CE%BF%CE%B8%CE%AE%CE%BA%CE%B7-%CE%B5%CE%BB%CE%BB%CE%AC%CE%B4%CE%BF%CF%82-%CE%BC%CE%B5-%CE%AC%CE%BB%CE%BB%CE%B1/>

Summary: A news item about the collaboration of the NLG with the NPO "Me Alla Matia" which was founded in June 2018 by a blind lawyer and a group of disabled young people, who were self-organized, with the ultimate goal of claiming inclusion and accessibility through social action. The NLG assigned to the NPO a study for the functionality check of the equipment for disabled persons in the NLG. The NPO produced a report after field work in the facilities of NLG and organisation of focus groups with end users.

Role of library: Check of the functionality of library's equipment for disabled persons.

Type of action: Support of a NPO dedicated to inclusion and accessibility and study of the current status of the equipment for disabled persons.

Guidelines for accessibility by the National Library of Greece (NLG) [available in Greek]

<https://www.nlg.gr/static-page/protypa-prosvasimotitas-gia-amea/>

Summary: The NLG has set the guidelines to libraries in Greece for the creation and dissemination of resources that are accessible to disabled persons.

Role of library: Provision of guidelines and standards

Type of action: Guidelines

Panteion University Library: Support for people with disabilities

<https://library.panteion.gr/en/services/services-for-disabled-people/>

Summary: Panteion University Library seeks to be fully inclusive to all library users and ensure that all information resources are equally accessible to all users regardless of any physical or mental impairment they may have. To facilitate access the library is physically accessible, provides special equipment, and offers textbooks in accessible digital formats to users who are blind, have low vision or are otherwise disabled.

Role of library: Provision of physical accessibility, special equipment and textbooks in accessible digital formats.

Type of action: Supportive to the needs of persons with disabilities.

Dis/misinformation in conflict

Activities of Ukrainian libraries to combat manipulation of public opinion in conditions of martial state [available in Ukrainian]

Nudyshchuk, G., & Horban, Y. (2024), Activities of Ukrainian libraries to combat manipulation of public opinion in conditions of martial state, Collection of Scientific Papers 'SCIENTIA', (November 22, 2024; Athens, Greece), 402-406. URL:

<https://previous.scientia.report/index.php/archive/article/view/2248>

Summary: This scientific publication analyses the practices of Ukrainian libraries in disseminating truthful information and countering disinformation during martial law. It describes practices and mechanisms for adapting the library environment to new challenges and crises in emergency situations.

Role of library: Libraries' role to safeguard the truth in information dissemination during war time

Type of action: Adaptation of libraries to the new reality imposed by conflicts, countering disinformation

Public libraries of Ukraine as entities of information security in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war [available in Ukrainian]

Nudyshchuk, G., & Horban, Y. (2025).\, Public libraries of Ukraine as entities of information security in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war. Collection of Scientific Papers 'ΛΟΓΟΣ', (December 13, 2024; Zurich, Switzerland), 409-412.

<https://doi.org/10.36074/logos-13.12.2024.088>

Summary: A brief analytical note on the role of public libraries in ensuring information security and countering propaganda during wartime

Role of library: Libraries' role to safeguard the truth in information dissemination during war time and counter propaganda
Type of action: Adaptation of libraries to the new reality imposed by conflicts, ensuring information security

Anti-misinformation as a direction of library practice [\[available in Ukrainian\]](#)

Buchkovska, O., Anti-misinformation as a direction of library practice, International scientific journal 'EDUCATION AND SCIENCE', Issue 2(35). URL: <https://msu.edu.ua/educationandscience/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/Протидія-дезінформації-як-напрямок-бібліотечної-практики-1.pdf>

Summary: This paper analyses the forms, methods, and means that libraries can use to counter information war, emphasizing the role of libraries in protecting the information space in wartime. It describes practices for libraries to counter disinformation in emergency conditions.

Role of library: Libraries' role to safeguard information space in the emergency conditions that are imposed in conflicts.

Type of action: Adaptation of libraries to the new reality imposed by conflicts, ensuring information security and countering misinformation

Public libraries of Ukraine as a component of information resistance to Russian aggression [\[available in Ukrainian\]](#)

Novalska, T. V., Horban, Y. I., Bachynska, N. A., & Prystai, H. I. (2024), Public libraries of Ukraine as a component of information resistance to Russian aggression, Bulletin of the Kharkiv State Academy of Culture, (65), 69-82. <https://doi.org/10.31516/2410-5333.065.05>

Summary: The article examines the role of public libraries in Ukraine as a component of informational resistance to Russian aggression and their contribution to strengthening national self-awareness. Libraries continue to remain powerful centers of functioning, preservation and popularization of knowledge and culture. They contribute to the formation of a comfortable information space, the promotion of patriotic values in society.

Role of library: Public libraries can support the spiritual values of Ukrainian society, strengthen public consciousness and ensure information resistance to Russian aggression.

Type of action: Supporting the Ukrainian people to resist the Russian aggression during the wartime.

Public libraries of Ukraine as centers of counteraction to Russian propaganda in times of war [\[available in Ukrainian\]](#)

Nudyshchuk, H. (2024), Public libraries of Ukraine as centres of counteraction to Russian propaganda in times of war, [Ukrainian Journal of Library and Information Science, (14), 177-188. <https://doi.org/10.31866/2616-7654.14.2024.318335>

Summary: A scientific publication about the adaptation of public libraries in Ukraine to a new social role that is imposed by the war: countering Russian propaganda and supporting information security during the war

Role of library: Libraries role in countering disinformation in emergency conditions

Type of action: Adapting social roles and working methods in emergency situations

Scientific Library of the National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine [\[available in Ukrainian\]](#)

<https://nubip.edu.ua/node/114011>

Summary: A visit and a workshop by the Director of the Scientific Library of the National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine to Irpin Vocational College and its library. The topic of the workshop was the use of the digital library, the "Electronic Document Delivery" service, and other open resources that should be used to provide information support for the educational process remotely during the war by college librarians. Moreover, at the end of the visit, a document was signed about the main ways of cooperation and assistance between libraries of higher education institutions under martial law.

Role of library: Promote accurate information and open access to knowledge during the war

Type of action: Workshop, guidelines for cooperation between academic libraries under martial law.

Libraries of Kharkiv Region under Martial Law [\[available in Ukrainian\]](#)

<https://library.kname.edu.ua/638-proekt-biblioteki-kharkivshchini-v-umovakh-voennogo-stanu>

Summary: In the framework of the multi-platform project "Libraries of the Kharkiv Region under Martial Law", which is implemented by specialists of the V. G. Korolenko Kharkiv State Scientific Library in partnership with members of the Kharkiv Regional Branch (Branch) of the Ukrainian Library Association, librarians-documentarians record the consequences of the war.

Role of library: The libraries contribute to public awareness about the consequences of the war, hence countering disinformation and preserving cultural heritage

Type of action: Recording, digital archive

Media Chronograph [\[available in Ukrainian\]](#)

<https://library.uhsp.edu.ua/2023/02/24/rik-vijny-v-ukrayini-vystoyimo-peremozhemo-knygozbirnya-universytetu-proponuye-vashij-uvazi-mediahronograf-do-richnytsi-povnomasshtabnogo-vtorgnennya-rosiyan/>

Summary: The Library of the Hryhoriy Skovoroda University in Pereyaslav (Ukraine) created a media chronograph "The Year of War in Ukraine: We Will Stand, We Will Win!" to mark the anniversary of the full-scale Russian invasion

Role of library: The library served as a commemorative and educational hub, documenting the impact of the war through curated multimedia content.

Type of action: Awareness-raising initiative using digital storytelling to foster remembrance and resilience.

The Living Library Project: Meeting with Warrior Oleksiy Lukyanets [\[available in Ukrainian\]](#)

<https://library.kubg.edu.ua/pro-biblioteku/podii-ta-novyny/682-proiekt-zhyva-biblioteka-zustrich-z-voinom-oleksiem-lukiantsem.html>

Summary: On March 11, 2025, a meeting (that was broadcasted) was held at Grinchenko University as part of the "Living Library" project, the guest of which was hero-defender Oleksiy Lukyanets. This project, launched in Denmark, provides an opportunity to "read" real people - listen to their stories, communicate, ask questions, and learn about unique experiences firsthand. The guest spoke about his life path and military experience after Russia's invasion in Ukraine.

Role of library: In the framework of this project, the library gave voice to a warrior that spoke to the public about the everyday military life but also shared his thoughts on the future and post-war recovery.

Type of action: Public lectures, discussions, sharing of information and experiences

Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Lithuania: Media and Information Literacy Programme (MIRKT) [\[available in Lithuanian\]](#)

<https://mirkt.bibliotekavisiems.lt/>

Summary: A program of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Lithuania for media and information literacy in which the libraries prepared resources, organised training events and disseminated information.

Role of library: Supportive to the program as a reliable source of knowledge.

Type of action: Provision of resources and training.

'Whose is Crimea?' or What Content Are International Databases of Scientific Publications Filled with

Tymofieieva, H. V., Opryshko T. S., & Bulvinksa, O. I. (2024). 'Whose is Crimea?' or What Content Are International Databases of Scientific Publications Filled with. University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings, (9), 9–15. https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2024_316850

Summary: A scientific article discussing the issue of "mimicry under Ukrainian scientific publications" in the occupied territories (using the example of scientific journals of universities in occupied Crimea)

Role of library: The community of library professionals in Ukraine record facts of "mimicry under the guise of Ukrainian publications" and formulate arguments for the exclusion of these publications from international registers.

Type of action: An article about misinformation in war (mimicry under the Ukrainian edition)

Open data/science

Digital archive of documents about the Russian-Ukrainian war [\[available in Ukrainian\]](#)

<http://digitalarchivewar.korolenko.kharkov.com/>

Summary: "Digital Archive of Documents on the Russian-Ukrainian War" is a collection of documents from verified open Internet sources (photos, videos and text materials) that was initiated by the Ukrainian Library Association and implemented by libraries of Ukraine. The resource was created with the aim of preserving historical memory and making information accessible to a wide range of users.

Role of library: Preservation and verification of facts in emergency war conditions.

Type of action: Digital archive

Ukraine's security in the context of Russian armed aggression [\[available in Ukrainian\]](#)

<https://oth.nlu.org.ua/?p=10951>

Summary: The Yaroslav the Wise National Library of Ukraine conducted a study "Public Libraries of Ukraine in Conditions of Russian Armed Aggression" to monitor the state of public libraries in the regions during the Russian armed aggression as of December 31, 2024 and analyze its impact on the activities of public libraries in Ukraine.

Role of library: Adaptation and changes of libraries in emergency conditions. An example of how the Library collects and classifies open data about public libraries of Ukraine in conditions of Russian armed aggression.

Type of action: Study about the impact of war on the public libraries in Ukraine.

Critical Steps in Data Management During a Crisis

Black, M., Moncada, K., & Herstad, K. (2021). Critical steps in data management during a crisis. *Cytometry Part A*, 99 (1), 60-67. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cyto.a.24265>

Summary: A scientific article about two data management systems that have been successful during the current emergency created by the pandemic, specifically remote access and automated data transfer.

Role of library: Data stewardship role

Type of action: Provision of best practices and guidance

Extending the CARE Principles: Managing Data for Vulnerable Communities in Wartime and Humanitarian Crises

Suchikova, Y., & Nazarovets, S. (2025), Extending the CARE Principles: managing data for vulnerable communities in wartime and humanitarian crises. *Scientific Data*, 12(1), 420. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04756-9>

Summary: This essay explores the application of CARE principles (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) to wartime contexts, with a particular focus on internally displaced persons (IDPs) and civilians living under occupation.

Role of library: University library-led data governance proposal.

Type of action: Framework adaptation and advocacy.

Data Policy for Times of Crisis (DPTC) – CODATA

<https://codata.org/initiatives/data-policy/dptc/>

Summary: A global project on developing guidance, a checklist, and a factsheet as contributions to the UNESCO Open Science Toolkit (UNESCO-CODATA DPTC). An academic-policy interface for data governance in time of crisis.

Role of library: Libraries are among the stakeholders.

Type of action: Policy development and consultation.